

A209 12-JUN-92

Run no. F1

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 2401
Mean 3345.84
Standard dev 6.67041
Max value 3371.77
Min value 3339.48

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 2401
Mean 38.0575
Standard dev 6.25629
Max value 40.5366
Min value 0.000000

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 2401
Mean -23.9288
Standard dev 3.90723
Max value 0.000000
Min value -25.0956

1 second averages

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Run no. F1

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 2401
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 2401
Mean 39.0976
Standard dev 0.889660
Max value 40.6087
Min value 37.5853

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 2401
Mean -24.5772
Standard dev 0.301283
Max value -23.9974
Min value -25.1131

1 second averages

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Run no. F1

FWVS DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 573
No. of obs 2401
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 2401
Mean 1.160548e-06
Standard dev 1.012236e-05
Max value 2.020473e-04
Min value 0.000000

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 2401
Mean 1.153236e-02
Standard dev 8.747073e-03
Max value 0.185535
Min value 9.999998e-03

1 second averages

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Run no. F1

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 2401
Mean 7.868235e-02
Standard dev 1.297859e-02
Max value 0.190175
Min value 5.475000e-02

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 2401
Mean 45.5769
Standard dev 61.0512
Max value 423.172
Min value 1.50784

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 2401
Mean 67.9568
Standard dev 9.43432
Max value 107.261
Min value 54.9384

1 second averages

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Run no. F2

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 2438
Mean 45.5858
Standard dev 32.4172
Max value 112.282
Min value 17.5279

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 2438
Mean 38.0029
Standard dev 5.83565
Max value 39.5855
Min value 0.000000

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 2438
Mean -22.8082
Standard dev 3.50556
Max value 0.000000
Min value -23.8052

1 second averages

A209 12-JUN-92

Run no. F2

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 2438
Mean 183.495
Standard dev 32.7397
Max value 251.629
Min value 154.005

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 2438
Mean 38.9850
Standard dev 0.314339
Max value 39.6891
Min value 38.6204

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 2438
Mean -23.3489
Standard dev 0.234585
Max value -23.0210
Min value -23.8069

1 second averages

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Run no. F2

FWVS DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 573
No. of obs 2438
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 2438
Mean 1.070820e-03
Standard dev 6.586221e-03
Max value 9.455746e-02
Min value 4.165390e-07

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 2438
Mean 2.57854
Standard dev 14.0266
Max value 133.533
Min value 9.999998e-03

1 second averages

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Run no. F2

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 2438
Mean 0.114815
Standard dev 1.651745e-02
Max value 0.321406
Min value 9.705499e-02

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 2438
Mean 159.556
Standard dev 50.0594
Max value 484.922
Min value 25.7355

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 2438
Mean 32.2772
Standard dev 1.59580
Max value 35.9086
Min value 29.1628

24:10:39 24:20:48 24:30:57 24:41:06 24:51:16
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

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Run no. F3a

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 779
Mean 76.8149
Standard dev 41.1659
Max value 144.371
Min value 25.3868

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 779
Mean 26.0044
Standard dev 17.8356
Max value 38.2747
Min value 0.000000

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 779
Mean -16.2450
Standard dev 11.1422
Max value 0.000000
Min value -24.0147

1 second averages

A209 12-JUN-92

Run no. F3a

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 779
Mean 211.363
Standard dev 41.6582
Max value 280.962
Min value 160.014

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 779
Mean 38.2953
Standard dev 3.175347e-02
Max value 38.3466
Min value 38.2301

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 779
Mean -23.8224
Standard dev 0.121841
Max value -23.5753
Min value -24.0158

1 second averages

A209 12-JUN-92

Run no. F3a

FWVS DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 573
No. of obs 779
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 779
Mean 3.688072e-04
Standard dev 1.323104e-03
Max value 2.216458e-02
Min value 0.000000

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 779
Mean 1.52129
Standard dev 8.29143
Max value 138.098
Min value 9.999998e-03

1 second averages

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Run no. F3a

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 779
Mean 0.110484
Standard dev 1.111900e-02
Max value 0.281340
Min value 9.741166e-02

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 779
Mean 164.462
Standard dev 25.7659
Max value 236.922
Min value 80.5318

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 779
Mean 32.8695
Standard dev 1.27135
Max value 35.8947
Min value 29.1907

1 second averages

A209 12-JUN-92

Run no. F3b

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 1176
Mean 72.4810
Standard dev 36.2970
Max value 126.748
Min value 20.7633

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 1176
Mean 37.2575
Standard dev 4.23688
Max value 37.7814
Min value 0.000000

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 1176
Mean -23.6654
Standard dev 2.69968
Max value 0.000000
Min value -24.2897

1 second averages

A209 12-JUN-92

Run no. F3b

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 1176
Mean 205.061
Standard dev 36.9566
Max value 261.649
Min value 149.999

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 1176
Mean 37.8106
Standard dev 3.829001e-02
Max value 37.8529
Min value 37.7168

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 1176
Mean -23.9672
Standard dev 0.222200
Max value -23.4991
Min value -24.2935

1 second averages

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Run no. F3b

FWVS DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 573
No. of obs 1176
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 1176
Mean 3.279804e-04
Standard dev 1.487539e-03
Max value 3.038373e-02
Min value 4.479061e-07

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 1176
Mean 1.12533
Standard dev 6.74649
Max value 133.088
Min value 9.999998e-03

1 second averages

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Run no. F3b

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 1176
Mean 0.111587
Standard dev 1.422102e-02
Max value 0.248760
Min value 9.443057e-02

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 1176
Mean 161.832
Standard dev 34.6704
Max value 254.574
Min value 40.7650

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 1176
Mean 33.8409
Standard dev 1.57439
Max value 36.5786
Min value 30.0413

1 second averages

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Run no. F1

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 5233
Mean 5814.69
Standard dev 606.949
Max value 6103.17
Min value 3575.99

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 5233
Mean 33.4467
Standard dev 1.88887
Max value 36.5560
Min value 30.2711

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 5233
Mean -26.7405
Standard dev 0.574580
Max value -25.5493
Min value -27.6268

1 second averages

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Run no. F1

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 5233
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 5233
Mean 33.4576
Standard dev 1.88894
Max value 36.5669
Min value 30.2815

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 5233
Mean -26.7430
Standard dev 0.574858
Max value -25.5516
Min value -27.6297

1 second averages

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Run no. F1

FWS DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 573
No. of obs 5233
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 5233
Mean 6.186136e-06
Standard dev 8.687894e-05
Max value 5.192757e-03
Min value 0.000000

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 5233
Mean 4.045649e-02
Standard dev 0.413251
Max value 24.9737
Min value 9.999998e-03

1 second averages

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Run no. F1

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 5233
Mean 8.911530e-02
Standard dev 3.540956e-02
Max value 0.415883
Min value 5.475000e-02

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 5233
Mean 31.8651
Standard dev 18.5571
Max value 165.863
Min value 9.999998e-03

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 5233
Mean 66.1604
Standard dev 8.78324
Max value 90.7814
Min value 50.8541

1 second averages

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Run no. F2

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 2641
Mean 5.15368
Standard dev 44.5554
Max value 214.562
Min value -73.1725

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 2641
Mean 28.8787
Standard dev 0.166641
Max value 29.3712
Min value 28.5977

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 2641
Mean -28.0844
Standard dev 0.240760
Max value -27.6218
Min value -28.5523

1 second averages

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Run no. F2

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 2641
Mean 91.0462
Standard dev 45.8690
Max value 310.300
Min value 14.3978

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 2641
Mean 28.8783
Standard dev 0.175413
Max value 29.3818
Min value 28.6071

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 2641
Mean -28.0576
Standard dev 0.246106
Max value -27.6254
Min value -28.5563

1 second averages

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Run no. F2

FWVS DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 573
No. of obs 2641
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 2641
Mean $1.055334e-05$
Standard dev $1.530843e-05$
Max value $2.847803e-04$
Min value $3.653732e-07$

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 2641
Mean 0.120257
Standard dev $8.411738e-02$
Max value 0.488345
Min value $9.999998e-03$

1 second averages

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Run no. F2

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 2641
Mean 9.812599e-02
Standard dev 1.244286e-02
Max value 0.186350
Min value 7.395142e-02

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 2641
Mean 41.1669
Standard dev 15.1150
Max value 103.991
Min value 12.1769

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 2641
Mean 31.0919
Standard dev 1.79318
Max value 35.5567
Min value 27.4531

1 second averages

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Run no. F3

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 1618
Mean 1719.36
Standard dev 61.0260
Max value 1764.88
Min value 1373.70

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 1618
Mean 28.6204
Standard dev 6.026579e-02
Max value 28.7364
Min value 28.5073

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 1618
Mean -28.0429
Standard dev 0.220590
Max value -27.6603
Min value -28.3725

1 second averages

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Run no. F3

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 1618
Mean 38.8167
Standard dev 237.852
Max value 1495.68
Min value 0.000000

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 1618
Mean 28.6308
Standard dev 5.883904e-02
Max value 28.7453
Min value 28.5160

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 1618
Mean -28.0472
Standard dev 0.219702
Max value -27.6577
Min value -28.3767

1 second averages

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Run no. F3

FWVS DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 573
No. of obs 1618
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 1618
Mean $6.786574e-07$
Standard dev $8.703901e-07$
Max value $8.498351e-06$
Min value 0.000000

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 1618
Mean $1.053920e-02$
Standard dev $4.963290e-03$
Max value 0.189321
Min value $9.999998e-03$

1 second averages

12:38:44 12:45:28 12:52:12 12:58:56 13:05:41
TIME (GMT)

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Run no. F3

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 1618
Mean $8.040155e-02$
Standard dev $8.539538e-03$
Max value 0.126128
Min value $6.351364e-02$

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 1618
Mean 50.2492
Standard dev 31.0303
Max value 275.011
Min value 12.0200

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 1618
Mean 57.0489
Standard dev 7.67282
Max value 74.1756
Min value 36.4647

1 second averages

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Run no. F4

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 2909
Mean 250.710
Standard dev 281.734
Max value 705.887
Min value -55.5525

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 2909
Mean 28.5165
Standard dev 6.229832e-02
Max value 28.6422
Min value 28.3878

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 2909
Mean -28.0136
Standard dev 0.201706
Max value -27.6294
Min value -28.3735

1 second averages

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Run no. F4

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 2909
Mean 335.873
Standard dev 287.171
Max value 801.714
Min value 25.1331

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 2909
Mean 28.5252
Standard dev 6.276990e-02
Max value 28.6516
Min value 28.3882

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 2909
Mean -28.0171
Standard dev 0.202418
Max value -27.6325
Min value -28.3781

1 second averages

13:16:05 13:28:12 13:40:19 13:52:26 14:04:33
TIME (GMT)

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Run no. F4

FWVS DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 573
No. of obs 2909
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 2909
Mean 8.879174e-06
Standard dev 1.636443e-05
Max value 4.477790e-04
Min value 4.250261e-07

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 2909
Mean 0.100947
Standard dev 9.006348e-02
Max value 0.407822
Min value 9.999998e-03

1 second averages

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Run no. F4

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 2909
Mean 9.454253e-02
Standard dev 1.276726e-02
Max value 0.179380
Min value 6.105995e-02

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 2909
Mean 43.3536
Standard dev 80.5117
Max value 2418.29
Min value 7.66753

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 2909
Mean 33.7921
Standard dev 1.99630
Max value 38.7202
Min value 26.4703

1 second averages

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Run no. F5a

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 127
Mean 1388.25
Standard dev 1.83997
Max value 1392.61
Min value 1384.92

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 127
Mean 28.3686
Standard dev 1.058631e-02
Max value 28.3869
Min value 28.3507

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 127
Mean -27.9212
Standard dev 3.674119e-02
Max value -27.8589
Min value -27.9846

1 second averages

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Run no. F5a

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 127
Mean 1495.31
Standard dev 0.666928
Max value 1495.68
Min value 1493.30

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 127
Mean 28.3772
Standard dev 1.049961e-02
Max value 28.3954
Min value 28.3594

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 127
Mean -27.9261
Standard dev 3.671808e-02
Max value -27.8637
Min value -27.9894

1 second averages

A210 14-JUN-92

Run no. F5a

FWVS DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 573
No. of obs 127
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 127
Mean 8.317040×10^{-7}
Standard dev 1.004125×10^{-6}
Max value 3.246753×10^{-6}
Min value 0.000000

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 127
Mean 1.082908×10^{-2}
Standard dev 3.431388×10^{-3}
Max value 3.905869×10^{-2}
Min value 9.999998×10^{-3}

1 second averages

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Run no. F5a

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 127
Mean $7.594018e-02$
Standard dev $6.695646e-03$
Max value 0.107034
Min value $6.550834e-02$

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 127
Mean 43.9684
Standard dev 9.86875
Max value 70.4156
Min value 14.3144

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 127
Mean 56.7708
Standard dev 2.75665
Max value 60.1130
Min value 50.6205

1 second averages

A210 14-JUN-92

Run no. F5b

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 911
Mean 1722.17
Standard dev 71.7193
Max value 1754.95
Min value 1398.80

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 911
Mean 28.5012
Standard dev 7.226706e-02
Max value 28.6595
Min value 28.3872

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 911
Mean -28.2482
Standard dev 0.224673
Max value -27.8203
Min value -28.5486

1 second averages

A210 14-JUN-92

Run no. F5b

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 911
Mean 50.8958
Standard dev 271.320
Max value 1495.68
Min value 0.000000

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 911
Mean 28.5112
Standard dev 7.313990e-02
Max value 28.6689
Min value 28.3959

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 911
Mean -28.2511
Standard dev 0.224436
Max value -27.8230
Min value -28.5533

1 second averages

A210 14-JUN-92

Run no. F5b

FWVS DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 573
No. of obs 911
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 911
Mean 7.218406×10^{-7}
Standard dev 1.101533×10^{-6}
Max value 1.497289×10^{-5}
Min value 0.000000

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 911
Mean 1.152119×10^{-2}
Standard dev 8.619962×10^{-3}
Max value 0.180125
Min value 9.999998×10^{-3}

1 second averages

A210 14-JUN-92

Run no. F5b

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 911
Mean 9.024658e-02
Standard dev 1.060607e-02
Max value 0.145097
Min value 6.396955e-02

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 911
Mean 146.984
Standard dev 83.1936
Max value 313.743
Min value 12.4700

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 911
Mean 75.9073
Standard dev 16.4103
Max value 93.8565
Min value 47.1481

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F1

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 2626
Mean 2709.04
Standard dev 13.6188
Max value 2789.46
Min value 2684.40

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 2626
Mean 33.7348
Standard dev 0.735095
Max value 34.5950
Min value 32.1980

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 2626
Mean -22.8256
Standard dev 1.02844
Max value -21.7792
Min value -24.4566

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F1

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 2626
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 2626
Mean 33.7017
Standard dev 0.693439
Max value 34.6046
Min value 32.2092

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 2626
Mean -22.6826
Standard dev 0.869053
Max value -21.7817
Min value -24.4614

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F1

FWVS DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 573
No. of obs 2626
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 2626
Mean $1.209071e-06$
Standard dev $1.411217e-06$
Max value $8.412509e-06$
Min value 0.000000

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 2626
Mean $1.026489e-02$
Standard dev $3.746583e-03$
Max value 0.187403
Min value $9.999998e-03$

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F1

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 2626
Mean $8.059670e-02$
Standard dev $9.589569e-03$
Max value 0.188733
Min value $5.475000e-02$

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 2626
Mean 94.9050
Standard dev 82.7734
Max value 348.955
Min value $9.999998e-03$

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 2626
Mean 80.6817
Standard dev 26.6402
Max value 126.972
Min value 49.1263

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F2

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 2499
Mean 242.106
Standard dev 223.911
Max value 758.922
Min value -57.7159

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 2499
Mean 30.4984
Standard dev 9.693890e-02
Max value 30.7158
Min value 30.3494

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 2499
Mean -20.5890
Standard dev 0.218937
Max value -20.3481
Min value -20.9860

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F2

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 2499
Mean 320.403
Standard dev 228.764
Max value 847.217
Min value 14.2159

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 2499
Mean 30.5275
Standard dev 9.466369e-02
Max value 30.7247
Min value 30.3546

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 2499
Mean -20.6483
Standard dev 0.194879
Max value -20.3340
Min value -20.9897

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F2

FWVS DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 573
No. of obs 2499
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 2499
Mean 8.469058e-05
Standard dev 1.984469e-03
Max value 8.801305e-02
Min value 4.339231e-07

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 2499
Mean 0.589615
Standard dev 8.01966
Max value 362.506
Min value 9.999998e-03

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F2

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 2499
Mean 9.296370e-02
Standard dev 4.298491e-03
Max value 0.284310
Min value 8.532885e-02

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 2499
Mean 926.086
Standard dev 110.924
Max value 1445.52
Min value 394.735

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 2499
Mean 81.4634
Standard dev 2.35229
Max value 86.9029
Min value 75.7241

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F3

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 727
Mean 1488.10
Standard dev 80.1460
Max value 1526.11
Min value 940.385

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 727
Mean 28.8778
Standard dev 6.69239
Max value 30.5978
Min value 0.000000

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 727
Mean -19.6400
Standard dev 4.55429
Max value 0.000000
Min value -20.9999

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F3

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 727
Mean 1485.25
Standard dev 54.1333
Max value 1495.68
Min value 1037.75

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 727
Mean 30.4443
Standard dev 0.101159
Max value 30.6112
Min value 30.2889

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 727
Mean -20.7139
Standard dev 0.184647
Max value -20.4064
Min value -21.0354

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F3

FWVS DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 573
No. of obs 727
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 727
Mean 1.063121e-06
Standard dev 3.675371e-06
Max value 6.604419e-05
Min value 0.000000

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 727
Mean 1.079007e-02
Standard dev 6.825297e-03
Max value 0.185535
Min value 9.999998e-03

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F3

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 727
Mean $7.761922e-02$
Standard dev $3.609989e-03$
Max value $9.347257e-02$
Min value $6.837064e-02$

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 727
Mean 180.559
Standard dev 106.547
Max value 710.197
Min value 41.1743

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 727
Mean 90.0891
Standard dev 9.37828
Max value 107.221
Min value 73.2660

16:14:00 16:17:01 16:20:03 16:23:04 16:26:06

TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F4

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 1786
Mean 2941.75
Standard dev 227.419
Max value 3063.62
Min value 2053.85

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 1786
Mean 32.2913
Standard dev 1.01653
Max value 33.3674
Min value 0.000000

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 1786
Mean -20.8604
Standard dev 0.528757
Max value 0.000000
Min value -21.1859

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F4

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 1786
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 1786
Mean 32.3162
Standard dev 0.670711
Max value 33.3752
Min value 31.1642

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 1786
Mean -20.8749
Standard dev 0.188550
Max value -20.5683
Min value -21.1880

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F4

FWVS DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 573
No. of obs 1786
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 1786
Mean 2.155341e-06
Standard dev 1.066076e-06
Max value 8.328385e-06
Min value 0.000000

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 1786
Mean 1.020194e-02
Standard dev 1.403257e-03
Max value 3.710575e-02
Min value 9.999998e-03

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F4

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 1786
Mean 7.640518e-02
Standard dev 4.253450e-03
Max value 0.103817
Min value 6.679267e-02

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 1786
Mean 181.417
Standard dev 70.4873
Max value 549.762
Min value 77.0724

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 1786
Mean 129.241
Standard dev 8.44464
Max value 147.551
Min value 109.892

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F5a

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 331
Mean 176.617
Standard dev 190.005
Max value 582.349
Min value -69.2453

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 331
Mean 34.0241
Standard dev 5.522798e-02
Max value 34.1208
Min value 33.9293

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 331
Mean -21.5592
Standard dev 6.807553e-02
Max value -21.4425
Min value -21.6753

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F5a

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 331
Mean 263.838
Standard dev 193.141
Max value 677.324
Min value 14.3978

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 331
Mean 34.0316
Standard dev 5.541179e-02
Max value 34.1288
Min value 33.9370

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 331
Mean -21.5601
Standard dev 6.812757e-02
Max value -21.4436
Min value -21.6765

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F5a

FWVS DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 573
No. of obs 331
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 331
Mean 4.937108×10^{-5}
Standard dev 4.994740×10^{-5}
Max value 3.208839×10^{-4}
Min value 4.165121×10^{-7}

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 331
Mean 0.529305
Standard dev 0.388486
Max value 2.04341
Min value 9.999998×10^{-3}

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F5a

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 331
Mean $9.493352e-02$
Standard dev $2.741910e-03$
Max value 0.105213
Min value $9.096473e-02$

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 331
Mean 1427.36
Standard dev 195.619
Max value 1876.52
Min value 810.257

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 331
Mean 95.1472
Standard dev 12.1584
Max value 128.863
Min value 86.2732

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F5b

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 301
Mean 109.147
Standard dev 122.368
Max value 346.495
Min value -77.2291

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 301
Mean 30.2032
Standard dev 11.8437
Max value 34.8707
Min value 0.000000

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 301
Mean -19.5030
Standard dev 7.64787
Max value 0.000000
Min value -22.5366

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F5b

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 301
Mean 203.105
Standard dev 124.407
Max value 444.658
Min value 13.6700

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 301
Mean 34.8350
Standard dev 5.221804e-02
Max value 34.9256
Min value 34.7437

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 301
Mean -22.4867
Standard dev 6.014920e-02
Max value -22.3835
Min value -22.5903

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F5b

FWVS DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 573
No. of obs 301
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 301
Mean $4.561568e-05$
Standard dev $3.165130e-05$
Max value $3.748012e-04$
Min value $4.431555e-06$

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 301
Mean 0.611609
Standard dev 0.177897
Max value 1.18496
Min value 0.197397

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F5b

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 301
Mean 9.547812e-02
Standard dev 2.375357e-03
Max value 0.106104
Min value 8.968171e-02

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 301
Mean 738.260
Standard dev 114.261
Max value 997.812
Min value 490.682

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 301
Mean 82.3546
Standard dev 4.26051
Max value 106.806
Min value 78.8193

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F5c

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 457
Mean 211.682
Standard dev 193.196
Max value 610.194
Min value -84.3574

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 457
Mean 35.7207
Standard dev 7.587212e-02
Max value 35.8529
Min value 35.5902

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 457
Mean -23.5395
Standard dev 9.941817e-02
Max value -23.3680
Min value -23.7111

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F5c

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 457
Mean 314.212
Standard dev 196.211
Max value 718.413
Min value 14.5798

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 457
Mean 35.7287
Standard dev 7.596273e-02
Max value 35.8611
Min value 35.5982

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 457
Mean -23.5400
Standard dev 9.944112e-02
Max value -23.3686
Min value -23.7121

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F5c

FWVS DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 573
No. of obs 457
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 457
Mean 3.047118×10^{-5}
Standard dev 5.683990×10^{-5}
Max value 7.157209×10^{-4}
Min value 4.430979×10^{-7}

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 457
Mean 0.327507
Standard dev 0.248924
Max value 3.16380
Min value 9.999998×10^{-3}

1 second averages

A211 15-JUN-92

Run no. F5c

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 457
Mean 9.507708e-02
Standard dev 4.564707e-03
Max value 0.108691
Min value 8.090353e-02

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 457
Mean 294.003
Standard dev 72.8740
Max value 476.314
Min value 166.932

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 457
Mean 62.7744
Standard dev 6.42721
Max value 91.2152
Min value 57.6893

1 second averages